

Determinants Affecting Training Service Quality: A Case Study Of Universities In Vietnam

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: August, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Training, Service, Quality, Universities, HCM, Vietnam</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5228488</p>	<p><i>Nowadays, the quality of products and services has long been considered a key factor to ensure the success and practical competitive advantage of organizations. The higher education institutions are recognized as part of the service industry and are becoming a fast-growing, highly competitive industry to cater to the growing needs of society. Dynamic national, regional and global developments have forced higher education institutions to transform rapidly, and these changes have received increasing attention over the past two decades. Students are considered primary customers of higher education. Besides, universities must continuously improve and the quality of training to meet the needs of learners, employers, and society. Thus, the paper is to identify factors affecting the training service quality of universities in Vietnam. The authors surveyed 800 students who are studying at many universities in Vietnam. The paper used structural equation modeling. Finally, five various factors were affecting the training service quality with 1% significance. Based on the research results, the author had managerial recommendations to improve the training service quality of universities in Vietnam for the following years.</i></p>

INTRODUCTION

According to Towley, J. K. (2018), the training service quality is defined as the characteristic of a series of inputs, processes, and outputs of the education and training system that provides satisfying services to meet learners' needs and the needs of learners society in terms of training. Currently, the demand for access to higher education is very significant. Many universities and training institutions increasingly fierce by Abdullah (2005). Therefore, improving the quality of training services becomes more and more urgent for the existence and development of each university. Improving the quality of training services is a process that should do continuously; the opinions on the quality of training services from students are indispensable in enhancing universities' quality of training services.

Besides, the quality of training services of universities in Vietnam is currently a big issue that is always paid special attention by society and the Government because the quality of training services is not high compared to other countries in the region and the world. This problem became more serious when a series of universities were established or upgraded in a short time. More than 20% of universities have been set or upgraded in about ten years. Reality showed the scale of universities' training had increased dramatically, while the number of teachers, facilities, training programs, etc., has not been improved much. Moreover, the trained students do not meet the needs and requirements of society. Thus, the paper is to identify the factors affecting the training service quality of universities in Vietnam.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Training service quality(TSQ)

According to DeShields et al. (2005), the quality of training services is a relative concept and is understood in many different ways, depending on the approach to the problem. Students, admissions centers, faculty and staff, government and funding agencies, accrediting bodies, and professionals define what they mean by service quality. In each position, people perceive the quality of training services in various aspects. Each different point of view will give other concepts of training service quality by Dhruv, G. F. (2012).

According to Abdullah (2006), higher education must create high service quality and student satisfaction to ensure sustainability in a competitive service environment. Higher education is defined as a "business market" that succeeds only when "customers" (students) are offered what they want to buy, at what they consider acceptable. When students are considered the "primary customers" of a university and are the direct recipients of the services provided, the quality of services assessed from the student's perspective

becomes a critical issue in the workplace management of the university by Trardona, B. M. (2017). According to Luo, S., N. et al. (2015), the training service quality is defined as a multi-directional concept that includes functions and activities such as training program, quality lecturers, teaching quality, facilities, support staff, management - administration, and interactive system by Parasuraman et al. (1985). Understanding "Training service quality" is a relative, dynamic, multidimensional concept with people in different positions may have other priorities when considering it.

Academic staff quality (ASQ)

According to San, M. R. (2017), the study related to Academic staff quality, lecturers evaluated for their teaching qualities and competence, which are: The teaching staff has ethical attributes to meet the professional requirements: Serious working style; compliance with discipline; always make efforts, unite, agree, support each other, overcome difficulties to complete the task. However, there are still many cases where the teaching staff does not strictly comply with the rules, regulations, etc., even violating them to the point of disciplinary action. A contingent of qualified lecturers who meet the requirements of assigned teaching tasks; There are no lecturers not completing their assignments due to limited teaching capacity by Nino, T. (2019). Lecturers are the most important and valuable learning resource for students. Teachers must have adequate knowledge and understanding of the subject they are teaching and have the necessary skills and teaching experience to impart and exchange that knowledge and understanding. Effectively in a teaching environment can get student feedback on their teaching. The training quality of an educational institution depends not only on the training program but also on the quality of the teaching staff. The quality of lecturers includes qualifications, professional knowledge, experience, teaching skills, and professional ethics. The teaching staff includes full-time and part-time professors, permanent faculty, and visiting faculty. In addition, the quality of teachers, the university needs to determine the number of lecturers to meet the requirements and needs of students as well as the unit by Nisar, M. et al. (2018). Based on the above, the authors had the hypothesis H1: There is a positive relationship (+) between academic staff quality (ASQ) and the training service quality of universities in Vietnam.

Hypothesis H1: Academic staff quality (ASQ) has a positive relationship with the training service quality of universities in Vietnam.

Training program (TP)

According to Panagiotis, L. (2014), the training program at a specific level of a discipline includes objectives, output standards; training content, methods and activities; conditions of physical - technical foundations, organizational structure, functions, tasks, and academic activities of the unit assigned to conduct training in that discipline. The training program should ensure teaching and learning methods, student assessment, and testing activities contribute to the achievement of expected learning outcomes. Taweena, S. and Chenin, C. (2018) had built a scale of training programs on the following aspects: diverse training programs with many different specialties, allowing students to continue to study at a higher level or switch majors easily, the university provides high-quality training programs, content that meets the practical requirements of the profession, combining professional knowledge and skills. The training program emphasizes subject outlines, timetables, teaching methods, processes, and assessment systems, has clear objectives and meets the requirements of knowledge standards, skills and attitudes. Based on the above, the authors had the hypothesis H2: There is a positive relationship (+) between academic staff quality (ASQ) and the training service quality of universities in Vietnam.

Hypothesis H2: Academic staff quality (ASQ) has a positive relationship with the training service quality of universities in Vietnam.

Quality of support staff (QSS)

According to Porter, S. J. (2018), the support staff need to pay attention to students understanding students' needs, creating a sense of peace of mind and safety for students, helping students fulfill their academic obligations. Sackoy, R. D. (2016), this factor is related to the performance of the lecturer's duties. According to Perisau S. R. (2017), the support aspect of the staff is an essential element for students to fulfill their academic obligations and to the duties and responsibilities performed by a team other than teachers (ability and willingness of administrative or support staff). Show respect, provide fair treatment and protect confidential information. The quality of training depends a lot on the interaction between lecturers and students by Baron, S. (2017). However, the lecturer cannot complete the job well without good support from the support staff. Support

staffs working for librarians, labs, computer labs, and other student support units. Based on the above, the authors had the hypothesis H3: There is a positive relationship (+) between the quality of support staff (QSS) and the training service quality of universities in Vietnam.

Hypothesis H3: Quality of support staff (QSS) has a positive relationship with the training service quality of universities in Vietnam.

Infrastructure and equipment (IAE)

According to Blance, G. N. (2017), the facilities are also closely related to teaching and learning methods. With good facilities to help apply the teaching method in small groups, the classrooms also need to be designed flexibly and appropriately. Learning resources such as computers, electronic portals, library materials, etc., need to be fully equipped to meet the needs of students and staff, and lecturers by Wayduk, S. H. (2013). In addition, the university needs to create a professional image, spacious and modern facilities, adequate and convenient teaching and learning support equipment. Besides, the class sizes are limited. Each student is well-taken care of studying and has many opportunities to be employed after graduation by Perisau S. R. (2017). Fully equipped learning facilities, modern teaching and learning support equipment. The university is equipped with software and hardware to meet student's training and lecturers' training and scientific research needs. Besides, the university has an information technology system to meet staff and students, staff, lecturers. And students have easy access to the network and computers on campus to make the most information technology for teaching, research, service, and management activities by Lewes, D. S. (2014). Based on the above, the authors had the hypothesis H4: There is a positive relationship (+) between infrastructure and equipment (IAE) and the training service quality of universities in Vietnam.

Hypothesis H4: Infrastructure and equipment (IAE) have a positive relationship with the training service quality of universities in Vietnam.

Teaching and learning methods (TLM)

According to Samzi, A. G. (2017), developing outstanding attitudes and soft skills thanks to students' active teaching method is possible. Zambi, A. J. (2018) showed the effectiveness of highly interactive training programs (active teaching methods): knowledge, thinking, and attitudes in similar programs. The interactive program has a significant change compared to the non-interactive program, especially in terms of skills. Active teaching methods bring much higher learning effectiveness than traditional teaching methods. Teachers talk less, spend more time engaging students in various activities in the classroom and outside the classroom. Only based on participation and experience can they truly understand and create awareness for themselves. Perhaps that's why Lewes, D. S. (2014) asserted: maximizing learning is always the result of maximizing attraction. Teaching and learning methods should encourage students to learn, learn how to learn, and instill the requirement of lifelong learning through a commitment to thoughtful inquiry, information processing skills, and a willingness to experiment with new ideas and ways of doing. Of course, there is no single method of teaching and learning that is suitable for all educational institutions by Nino, T. (2019). Universities need to consider carefully choosing teaching and learning methods for the program. Teaching and learning activities are built on the principle of directed compatibility to ensure the expected learning outcomes. Based on the above, the authors had the hypothesis H5: There is a positive relationship (+) between teaching and learning methods (TLM) and the training service quality of universities in Vietnam.

Hypothesis H5: Teaching and learning methods (TLM) have a positive relationship with the training service quality of universities in Vietnam.

Through reference to research models related to the above, with the actual training service quality at universities in Vietnam and the above research hypotheses, the authors proposed that the factors affecting the quality of training services are as follows.

Source: The authors proposed

FIGURE 1
A RESEARCH MODEL FOR FACTORS THE FACTORS AFFECTING THE TRAINING SERVICE QUALITY OF UNIVERSITIES IN VIETNAM

METHODS OF RESEARCH

The authors conducted two phases in the research process: qualitative research and quantitative research, detailed in 6 steps, as shown in figure 2.

Source: The authors proposed

FIGURE 2
A RESEARCH PROCESS FOR THE FACTORS AFFECTING THE TRAINING SERVICE QUALITY OF UNIVERSITIES IN VIETNAM

First of all, the authors identified the study's objectives, referred to the study overview, and defined the research problem. And the authors synthesized theories related to factors affecting the training service quality of universities in Vietnam by Hair, J., Anderson, R., Tatham, R., and Black, W. (2010).

Secondly, the author had a theoretical basis, practical basis, and related to studies. Besides, the author applied qualitative research for interviewing 11 experts in educational management. The authors revised the factors affecting the training service quality of universities in Vietnam and making a preliminary scale by Hair, J., Anderson, R., Tatham, R., and Black, W. (2010).

Thirdly, the authors applied the qualitative research: expert interview based on the preliminary survey for 50 educational leaders who were assessed as having the ability to do resources, knowledge and many years of experience in educational management.

Fourthly, the authors had a preliminary survey and an official survey. The author had tested: Cronbach's Alpha, exploratory factor analysis (EFA), an official scale. The authors used a preliminary scale to survey 50 leaders in Vietnam randomly. A sample of 50 to perform the reliability testing reliability of the scale to build an official ranking for the official survey for quantitative research by Hair, J., Anderson, R., Tatham, R., and Black, W. (2010).

Fifthly, the authors had the official survey for 800 students studying at many universities in Vietnam. The official survey was conducted by sending survey questionnaires with distributed 800 questionnaires and 760 votes collected by Hair, J., Anderson, R., Tatham, R., and Black, W. (2010). Besides, the authors had the official testing: Cronbach's Alpha, EFA, CFA. The authors collected and processed by SPSS 20.0 software to test the scale, explicitly trying Cronbach's alpha Hair, J., Anderson, R., Tatham, R., and Black, W. (2010). The authors had tested Structural Equation Modeling and Bootstrap for the official survey questionnaire and conduct the survey.

Finally, the authors had conclusions and policy implications.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Testing Cronbach's alpha for the training service quality of universities in Vietnam

Code	Training service quality (TSQ)	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
TSQ1	In general, students are satisfied with the quality of training services at the university	0.936
TSQ2	Students will continue to participate in their studies due to the quality of training services at the university	0.889
TSQ3	Students will recommend friends and relatives to study because of the quality of training services at the university	0.938
Cronbach's alpha: 0.946		

Source: The authors processed by SPSS 20.0

Table 1 showed that Cronbach's alpha for the training service quality of universities in Vietnam is 0.946. Specifically, Cronbach's alpha values of the training service quality (TSQ) of alpha if item deleted TSQ1 = 0.936, TSQ2 = 0.889, and TSQ3 = 0.938. Table 1 showed that for training service quality with Cronbach's alpha coefficient 0.946 and all observed variables are more significant than 0.6. The above result is excellent, so we accept it. So the authors did not remove any variable in the training service quality factor because there is a scaling coefficient above the allowable level.

Code	Academic staff quality (ASQ)	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
ASQ1	Lecturers design and implement consistent teaching and learning programs	0.940
ASQ2	Lecturers use a variety of teaching and learning methods and select the most appropriate testing and assessment methods to ensure the achievement of expected learning outcomes	0.962
ASQ3	Lecturers develop and use a variety of teaching aids/resources	0.958
ASQ4	Lecturers engage in research and provide services that benefit stakeholders	0.942
Cronbach's alpha is 0.962		
Code	Training program (TP)	Cronbach's Alpha
TP1	The training program has subjects built with a reasonable structure, sequence, and cohesion	0.802
TP2	The structure of the training program clearly shows the relationship and teaching progress of the primary, basic and specialized subjects	0.812
TP3	The training program has a flexible structure, allowing students to both delve into a major while keeping up to date with changes and advancements	0.843
TP4	The training program is periodically reviewed to ensure its relevance and up-to-date	0.799
Cronbach's alpha is 0.854		
Code	Quality of support staff (QSS)	Cronbach's Alpha
QSS1	Competence and professional qualifications of support staff to meet job requirements	0.940
QSS2	Support staff to meet training, research, and community service needs in both quality and quantity	0.958
QSS3	Staff support and help students to be satisfied with their role at university	0.949

QSS4	Support staff including library staff, laboratories, computer rooms to meet the learning and research needs of students	0.935
Cronbach's alpha is 0.959		
Infrastructure and equipment (IAE)		
IAE1	The university has enough facilities, including equipment, learning materials, and information technology systems	0.928
IAE2	Equipment is up-to-date, ready to use, and efficiently allocated	0.942
IAE3	The learning resources are selected and guaranteed to match the goals of the training program	0.944
IAE4	The university has built an electronic library that is regularly updated to keep up with advances in information and communication technology	0.930
Cronbach's alpha is 0.951		
Teaching and learning methods (TLM)		
TLM1	Teaching and learning activities promote lifelong learning	0.847
TLM2	The learning method emphasizes the ability to understand, not memorize, helping students remember longer	0.808
TLM3	Current teaching and learning methods are compatible with expected learning outcomes	0.863
TLM4	Teaching and learning methods designed to be suitable and diverse with the expected learning outcomes of students	0.824
Cronbach's alpha is 0.872		

Source: The authors processed by SPSS 20.0

Table 2 showed that Cronbach's alpha for the factors affecting the training service quality of universities in Vietnam is more than 0.6. Specifically, Cronbach's alpha values are respectively: the Academic staff quality (ASQ) is 0.962; the training program (TP) is 0.854; the quality of support staff (QSS) is 0.959; the infrastructure and equipment (IAE) are 0.951, and the teaching and learning methods (TLM) are 0.872. The authors did not remove any variable in the five factors of training service quality because of the scale coefficient above the allowable level.

TABLE 3		
KMO AND BARTLETT'S TEST FOR THE FACTORS AFFECTING THE TRAINING SERVICE QUALITY OF UNIVERSITIES IN VIETNAM		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0.826
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	17242.832
	df	253
	Sig.	0.000
Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings: Cumulative is 83.389%		

Source: The authors processed by SPSS 20.0

Table 3 showed that the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy (KMO) is 0.826 (>0.5). The KMO coefficient is 0.826, and the significance level (Sig) is 0.000, indicating that the factor analysis is consistent with the survey data of 800 students, but there are 760 students with valid answers.

Source: The authors processed by SPSS 20.0 and Amos

FIGURE 3

TESTING CFA FOR THE FACTORS AFFECTING THE TRAINING SERVICE QUALITY OF UNIVERSITIES IN VIETNAM

Figure 3 showed that the assessment of the scale of the factors affecting the training service quality of universities in Vietnam including: CMIN/DF = 4.212 (<5.0), GFI = 0.911 (>0.8), TLI = 0.953 (>0.9), CFI = 0.960 (> 0.9) and RMSEA = 0.065 (<0.08). Based on the CFA test results, The confirmatory factor analysis results are divided into six components. In which there are five factors affecting service quality.

Source: The authors processed by SPSS 20.0 and Amos

FIGURE 4

TESTING SEM FOR THE FACTORS AFFECTING THE TRAINING SERVICE QUALITY OF UNIVERSITIES IN VIETNAM

TABLE 4
TESTING COEFFICIENTS FOR FACTORS AFFECTING BUSINESS PERFORMANCE OF SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES IN HO CHI MINH CITY

Relationships	Unstandardized Estimate	Standardized Estimate	SE.	CR.	P	Results
TSQ <--- QSS	0.546	0.534	0.032	16.997	***	Accepted
TSQ <--- ASQ	0.101	0.096	0.033	3.087	0.002	Accepted
TSQ <--- IAE	0.121	0.122	0.031	3.889	***	Accepted
TSQ <--- TP	0.190	0.163	0.038	4.990	***	Accepted
TSQ <--- TLM	0.193	0.077	0.060	3.231	0.001	Accepted

Source: The authors processed by SPSS 20.0 and Amos

Table 4 showed five factors affecting the training service quality of universities in Vietnam with a significance level of 0.01. The results showed that all five the training service quality for a standardized estimate including the academic staff quality (0.096); the training program (0.163); the quality of support staff (0.534); the infrastructure and equipment (0.122); and the teaching and learning methods (0.077).

TABLE 5
TESTING BOOTSTRAP WITH 90.000 SAMPLES FOR THE FACTORS AFFECTING THE TRAINING SERVICE QUALITY OF UNIVERSITIES IN VIETNAM

Parameter	SE	SE-SE	Mean	Bias	SE-Bias
TSQ <--- QSS	0.038	0.001	0.542	-0.005	0.001
TSQ <--- ASQ	0.031	0.000	0.101	-0.001	0.001
TSQ <--- IAE	0.032	0.001	0.119	-0.003	0.001
TSQ <--- TP	0.041	0.001	0.186	-0.004	0.001
TSQ <--- TLM	0.056	0.001	0.187	-0.006	0.001

Source: The authors processed by SPSS 20.0 and Amos

Table 5 showed that the bootstrap test results are very good with a sample of 90.000 students for five factors affecting the training service quality of universities in Vietnam.

CONCLUSION & POLICY IMPLICATIONS

Conclusion

The quality of training service of universities of Vietnam is currently a big issue that is always paid special attention by society and the Government. This article studies the factors affecting the training service quality of universities. Thus, the authors surveyed 800 students who are looking at many universities in Vietnam. The paper used structural equation modeling. Finally, five various factors were affecting the training service quality with 1% significance. Research results showed that the quality of training service depended on many factors. Firstly, a university with good facilities will have better training services quality. Secondly, the method of teaching and studying was organized and managed well, significantly improved. Thirdly, the lecturer quality is also essential to the learners. The more qualified and responsible the teaching staff is, the better the quality of training will be. Fourthly, the learning environment also showed its essential role in improving the quality of training. The better the learning environment, the higher the quality of training. Finally, the training program, the quality of support services, and learners' capacity also impact the quality of training. The article also proposed some policy implications to enhance universities' quality of training service in Vietnam based on statistical analysis.

Policy implications

Based on research results and practical implementation of teaching and learning at universities in Vietnam, we make some recommendations as follows:

First of all, Managerial recommendations need to improve the quality of support staff (0.534). Academic advisors should pay more attention to their students, encourage passive students to join mass movements, help students become more confident in communication. Besides, job training and retraining need to continue to foster and improve the qualifications of the staff with short-term study programs at the university to supplement the missing skills for work, enhancing foreign language, informatics, and pedagogical skills. Moreover, universities should strengthen the connection of information exchange between faculty and staff of the faculty and students studying at the faculty through extracurricular programs, briefings; create a secure and timely information channel to solve the students' thoughts and aspirations immediately. University officials and staff need to be more polite when communicating with students. Politeness in communication is a crucial factor to help maintain a good relationship between people. So, in contact, there should be minimal politeness. Especially in the academic environment, students are recognized as highly educated, aware, and culturally qualified people, objects of frequent communication. Therefore, it is required that officials and employees have basic and essential communication skills to know how to build relationships in university and life, creating a brilliant, polite atmosphere.

Secondly, Managerial recommendations need to improve the training program (0.163). The training program: It is necessary to be flexible in the design of training programs, following the requirements of economic and social development to meet the needs of the labor market; On the other hand, it must meet the needs of learners. The curriculum and content of higher education in Vietnam are still outdated, built mainly by empiricism. The revision that has been and is underway has not been effective. Besides, the training programs and contents are still independent of each other, lacking the connection between educational levels. This recommendation leads to the situation: learn a lot, but new knowledge is not much. Learning has not met the equivalent level. Political subjects have a lot of time; it is necessary to change how to teach to achieve high efficiency and increase foreign languages, computer science, expertise, and practice. In addition, the university units continue to innovate teaching methods and forms in the direction of focusing on training self-study and self-research methods, promoting scientific research activities among students, implementing entrepreneurship education in universities.

Thirdly, Managerial recommendations need to improve the infrastructure and equipment (0.122). Universities need to design modern classrooms according to international standards. Universities should have large classrooms for lecturers to teach in class, and at the same time need to have small rooms for teaching assistants to correct students' assignments. These classrooms need to be equipped with air conditioning, good sound and light, a projector, etc. At the same time, they need to be fitted with an electronic library and connect with libraries in Vietnam and abroad. Universities continue strengthening facilities and creating conditions, mainly mechanisms, for universities to improve training and research capabilities. With training and retraining institutions and programs and textbooks, facilities are a fundamental premise to ensure and enhance the quality of training and retraining. As a rule, a university or institute built according to international standards must have

adequate facilities and financial resources large enough to cover quality research and teaching activities quantity efficiently. Infrastructure is not a decisive factor, but it plays an indispensable role in training and fostering. Finally, universities have the rapid application of new technologies, using multi-purpose tools, such as computers, projectors, electronic lectures, smart boards, electronic textbooks, especially teaching software. Organizing classes, assigning assignments, limiting time, checking lessons. Thus, universities continue providing materials, getting feedback, adjusting activities of lecturers and students, managing training sessions online, remotely necessary. On the other hand, universities need to improve the quality of the training to save the social costs of the movement in terms of both time and finance; at the same time, creating a foundation for international integration.

Fourthly, Managerial recommendations need to improve the academic staff quality (0.096). Universities continue to maintain student satisfaction scores in theoretical aspects; record cases where lecturers are not on time, late, or leave early to have a solution. Create a vibrant and engaging atmosphere in the lecture; organize and plan lessons; effective technical means for studies. It is necessary to introduce a reasonable salary discrimination policy to attract good lecturers to work for the university. It is required to create a multicultural environment in the management team and lecturers, link and exchange lecturers and students to learn and update new and advanced knowledge from different cultures and countries. Focus on building, fostering, and rationally using the contingent of teachers and educational administrators - the fundamental force participating in the construction and development of education, which plays a decisive role in the quality of education and training. To build a contingent of teachers with good moral qualities, good health, and strong political will to meet the requirements of the new era. Formulate planning and plan for training and fostering teachers in association with socio-economic development needs—universities based on assessing capacity, professional ethics, and work efficiency.

Finally, Managerial recommendations need to improve the teaching and learning methods (0.077). The class should not be held too crowded as it is today, the size should be about 20 to 40 students, and at the same time, it is necessary to combine closely between a team of good lecturers and capable teaching assistants. Universities should organize student assessments more scientifically. Specifically, universities need at least two official exams for a subject. Each exam must be at least 120 minutes long, especially the final exam. It is necessary to closely combine multiple-choice tests and essays, not to abuse the structure of the multiple-choice exam. Teaching how to learn, self-study, self-reading, self-knowledge, and creative teaching thinking, expression, and communication is more important than teaching knowledge. Not every university, subject, and lecturer should write and write a curriculum. The university's job is to build large libraries, buy many books, organize the translation of many professional documents. The teacher's job is to introduce and guide students with required documents or needs to read. On the other hand, information technology must contribute more actively and effectively in teaching and learning methods.

REFERENCES

- Abdullah (2005). HEDPERF versus SERVPERF: The quest for the ideal measuring instrument of service quality in the higher education sector. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 13(1), 305-328.
- Abdullah (2006). The development of HEDPERF: A new measuring instrument of service quality for the higher education sector. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 30(6), 569-581.
- Baron, S. (2017). Students perception of service quality in a UK university business and management faculty. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 8(2), 85-95.
- Blance, G. N. (2017). Searching for excellence in business education: an exploratory study of customer impressions of service quality. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 1(2), 172-179.
- DeShields, O. W., Kara, A., & Kaynak, E. (2005). Determinants of business student satisfaction and retention in higher education: Applying Herzberg's two-factor theory. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 19(1), 128-139.
- Dhruv, G. F. (2012). Understanding service convenience. *Journal of Marketing*, 6(6), 1-17.
- Hair, J., Anderson, R., Tatham, R., and Black, W. (2010). *Multivariate data analysis with readings*. US: Prentice-Hall: Upper Saddle River, NJ, USA.
- Lewes, D. S. (2014). A Student-centred Conceptual Model of Service Quality in Higher Education. *Quality in Higher Education*, 9(4), 169-185.
- Luo, S., N. & Jianying, G., Dan X. and Khurram, S. (2015). Factors Leading to Students' Satisfaction in the Higher Learning Institutions. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 3(1), 114-118.
- Nino, T. (2019). Factors Influencing Student Satisfaction in Higher Education, the Case of a Georgian State University. *Research Association for Interdisciplinary Studies*, 1(1), 40-54.
- Nisar, M., Shahid, J.K., and Fayaz, A.S. (2018). Effect of Service Quality on Customers Satisfaction: An

- Application of HEDPERF Model. *Review of Economics and Development Studies*, 2(2), 165-177.
- Panagiotis, L. (2014). A study of customer satisfaction in greek postal services. *International Conference on Social Sciences and Humanities*, 1(2), 280-290.
- Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V.A. & Berry, L.L. (1985). A conceptual model of Service Quality and Its Implications for Future Research. *Journal of Marketing*, 49(4), 41-50.
- Perisau S. R. (2017). Assessing service quality in universities of business. *International Journal of Quality and Reliability Management*, 4(3), 204-218.
- Porter, S. J. (2018). How do academic departments impact student satisfaction? Understanding the contextual effects of departments. *Research in Higher Education*, 4(2), 24-38.
- Sackoy, R. D. (2016). An empirical examination of a model of perceived service quality and satisfaction. *Journal of Retailing*, 7(2), 152-164.
- Samzi, A. G. (2017). Linking student satisfaction and service quality perceptions: the case of university education. *European Journal of Marketing*, 13(7), 28-40.
- San, M. R. (2017). A neural network approach for assessing quality in technical education: an empirical study. *International Journal of Productivity and Quality Management Decision*, 2(3), 187-196.
- Taweena, S. and Chenin, C. (2018). Factors influencing students' satisfaction based on the quality of training service at Bangkok University - Thailand. *Journal of Economics, Business, and Management*, 13(4), 70-78.
- Towley, J. K. (2018). Measuring customer satisfaction in higher education. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 6(4), 19-28.
- Trardona, B. M. (2017). Service quality perceptions in higher education institutions: the case of a Colombian university. *Journal of Marketing*, 6(6), 11-27.
- Wayduk, S. H. (2013). Gaining competitive advantages in higher education: analyzing the gap between expectations and perceptions of service quality. *International Journal of Value-Based Management*, 1(3), 22-32.
- Zambi, A. J. (2018). Total quality management and higher education in Malaysia. *Total Quality Management*, 9(5), 130-142.

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